

EVALUATION OF CRYO TMA/DMA FOR DETERMINING THE STIFFNESS PROPERTIES OF ADHESIVES AT CRYOGENIC TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

Two epoxy paste adhesives, one polyurethane paste-adhesive and one epoxy film adhesive, were tested for their ability to operate in bonded carbon composites joints which are exposed to a cryogenic environment as it is existent in a liquid hydrogen storage tank. Due to different coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE), a thermal mismatch occurs between the composite and adhesive layers which can lead to thermally induced cracks. Therefore, for the design of the bonding area the thermal and mechanical properties, including the CTE, of the adhesives are considered as key elements. The CTE of the adhesives was measured in a cryogenic TMA according to the ISO 11359-2 at temperatures from 4 K up to 350 K. The tensile properties of the adhesives were determined according to the DIN EN ISO 527-2 at 296 K and in liquid nitrogen (LN₂) at 77 K. In addition, the viscoelastic properties of the adhesives were determined in a temperature range from 173 K up to 473 K by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). All in all, the results show a quite similar thermo-mechanical behavior of the tested adhesives, with an increasing stiffness and a significantly decreasing thermal expansion coefficient with decreasing temperature.

1 INTRODUCTION

The demand for emission-free aviation is increasing and liquid hydrogen (LH₂) has a high potential as propellant for emission-free aircrafts. Therefore, intensive research into liquid hydrogen storage systems has begun, as weight-optimized storage is a key element in the implementation of emission-free aviation. Due to its lower specific density and the possibility for load-adapted fiber orientation, the structural weight of a liquid hydrogen tank can be significantly reduced by using carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP). [1] However, the assembly of such CFRP based components to an LH₂ storage tank is challenging in several ways such as by structure, tightness and other constraints, which become effective especially at the typical LH₂ storage temperature of 20 K. [2]

The thermo-mechanical behaviour of adhesives in cryogenic conditions has not been sufficiently investigated yet. There is a minor of studies, which deal with the determination of mechanical and fracture behaviour of adhesives for LH₂ steel and CFRP-Tank structures. [3, 4, 5] Furthermore, test methods for determination of mechanical properties of epoxy based composite materials in cryogenic conditions are not standardized yet and will be developed within the framework of this study [6, 7].

The main objective of this project is to develop resource-efficient processing, joining and assembly methods for CFRP LH₂ tanks based on simulation- and test-based verification of cryogenic bonded joints. Two epoxy paste adhesives, one polyurethane paste-adhesive and one epoxy film adhesive, were tested for their ability to bond CFRP composites, in the context of cryogenic hydrogen storage. The design of the bonding area requires consideration of the adhesives thermal and mechanical properties, including the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE).

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Test specimen preparation

The manufacturing and preparation of test specimens was conducted at Airbus Materials laboratory. While the processing of the film adhesive and prepreg adherent substrates was conducted using established standard procedures, the fabrication of test coupons made from adhesive pastes had to be optimized to reduce air entrapment and void formation within the adhesive bulk material. Figure 1 shows the preparation of the specimen for CTE, tensile strength test and DMA measurement.

Figure 1: Specimens manufacturing and preparation

Four variants of adhesives are tested having the following characteristics:

ID	Chemistry	Curing characteristics	Typical field of application
1	2-part epoxy paste	Hot curing	Structural bonding of composites
2	2-part epoxy paste	Cold & hot curing	Shimming & Bonding
3	2-part polyurethane paste	Cold curing & tempering	Multi-purpose e.g. insulation of cryo tanks
4	1-part epoxy film	Hot curing	Structural bonding of composites

Table 1: Variants of adhesives

2.2 Tensile Testing

Tensile tests were performed according to DIN EN ISO 527-2 for the evaluation of strength, stiffness and poisons ratio of the adhesive bulk material at the ILK of the TUD. For the testing at room temperature the majority of test specimens were mounted on a ZwickRoell Z2.5 testing machine equipped with a 2.5 kN load cell, a video extensometer and pneumatic clamps. However, a few specimens exposed such a high yield strength that the testing of those adhesive candidates required a switch to a Z250 testing machine with a 10 kN load cell and wedge sample holders.

Test speeds for 296 K are 1 mm/min (modulus up to 0.25 % elongation), then switch to 5 mm/min (strength, adhesive 1, 2 and 4) or 50 mm/min (strength adhesive 3, due to high elongation at break).

The tensile test at 77 K was performed on a Zwick 1475 universal testing machine using a 10 kN load cell with a specially developed test setup (Figure 2, left).

Cryogenically suitable strain gauges (HBM 1.5/350 XC11) on both sides of the specimen were used for strain measurement. The specimen is clamped using a knurled specimen holder, and the clamping force is achieved by two screws tightened to a nominal torque appropriate to the material – typically 8 Nm. This test setup thermally decouples the specimen environment from the testing machine and ensures testing with the specimen completely immersed in liquid nitrogen. After filling the fixture with nitrogen, the test has only been started when minimal nitrogen evaporation is observed, i.e., when all parts of the clamping system and the specimen have reached the test temperature of 77 K (see Figure 3). Due to the very low strains to fracture observed under cryogenic conditions, the test speed at 77 K was set to 1 mm/min for the entire test, contrary to the standard.

Figure 2: Testing device for tests at 77 K (left) and testing machine for tests at 296 K (right)

Figure 3: Clamps in assembly device after test

2.3 Thermo-mechanical analysis (TMA)

At FIBRE, the CTE was determined using expansion-probe TMA in a standard and cryogenic conditions following the ISO 11359-2 at temperatures from 4 K up to 350 K (see Figure 4). To ensure the cold temperatures during testing, the measurement chamber is placed in a helium closed loop cryostat. This requires a three times longer dilatometer than in a standard TMA. To compensate for this, an up to ten times higher load than described in the ISO standard has to be applied to the specimen. This again requires extreme care concerning the mechanical contact of the quartz glass dilatometer to the specimen. A controlled cooling rate of 0.5 K/min and a heating rate at 1 K/min were applied in order to get insights on the temperature-dependence.

All specimens were preconditioned in a standard TMA Q800 from TA Instruments. The preconditioning was conducted as follows:

1. Apply a load of 25 mN
2. Cool and equilibrate at 223 K
3. Heating run at 5 K/min to 343 K
4. Hold isotherm for 5 min
5. Cooling run at 5 K/min to 223 K
6. End of measurement

The samples were weighed before and after each conditioning step and each measurement to determine the changes in moisture content. The results show, that the moisture content has an influence above around 263 K, but not below. Nevertheless, the preconditioning was used to ensure equal conditions of the specimen before the cryogenic CTE measurement.

2.4 Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)

The temperature-modulus behavior tests (see Figure 5) were conducted using an Anton Paar MCR-502s rheometer in torsion mode according to ISO 6721-7 [8].

To perform the tests following settings have been used:

- Testing instrument: MCR-502s rheometer (Anton Paar Germany GmbH)
- Specimen shape: Rectangular bar with a gauge length of approximately 22 mm, a width of approximately 10 mm, and a thickness of approximately 2.2 mm
- Heating rate: 4 K/min
- Test atmosphere: Air
- Amplitude of the dynamic angular displacement θ_A : 0.1 %
- Test frequency: 1 Hz
- 5 Tests per material

Figure 4: Cryo-TMA test stand and specimen

Figure 5: DMA test setup

3 RESULTS

3.1 Tensile Testing

The results show a significant difference in the Young's modulus, which increases significantly with decreasing temperature. The strengths also tend to increase, but less significantly and not for all adhesives tested. The graphs in Figure 6 show the average values of the results from seven samples.

Figure 6: Temperature dependent strength and stiffness of adhesives at 296 K and 77 K

Figure 7: Representative stress-strain-curves at 296 K and 77 K

3.2 Thermo-mechanical analysis

The CTE results show a comparable decrease of the CTE with decreasing temperature, while the difference of the value is decreasing with lower temperature. In addition, at temperatures below 73 K a smaller decrease is visible, and the CTE of the various adhesives is similar. At temperatures below 93 K the CTE is remains almost constant for all adhesives.

Due to the higher load of 500 mN a delayed measurement signal in the area around the glass transition temperature (T_g) is generated, which leads to an incorrect output (see Figure 8, adhesive 3). Therefore, the determination of the CTE and glass transition must be decoupled. This means, in the cryogenic TMA the CTE is measured from 4 K up to T_g of each adhesive. Above T_g the CTE is determined in a standard TMA according to the ISO 11359-2. The glass transition temperature is shown in the results of the DMA in the following chapter.

Figure 8: Coefficient of thermal expansion of 4 adhesives

3.3 Dynamic mechanical analysis

Representative curves selected from the five result curves for the respective adhesive are shown in Figure 9. The typical glass transition temperatures are clearly visible. The glass transition temperature of the polyurethane adhesive is only slightly above room temperature, whereas the epoxy resins exhibit significantly higher glass transition temperatures. It is also clearly evident that the elastic moduli of all polymers increase with decreasing temperature; it should be noted that the scale is non-linear. This clearly supports the results of the tensile tests conducted at two selected temperatures.

Figure 9: Results of DMA test for 4 adhesives, representative curve of 5 samples selected

4 CONCLUSIONS

The stiffness properties of various epoxy adhesives were successfully determined using novel cryogenic testing procedures. In general, the results show a quite similar thermo-mechanical behavior of the tested epoxy adhesives at cryogenic temperatures. As the temperature decreases, all tested adhesives exhibit an increase in stiffness, with the polyurethane-based adhesive showing a particularly pronounced stiffening effect. While the epoxy adhesives respond in a very much comparable manner under cryogenic conditions, significant differences in individual properties remain. Most notably, the elongation at break decreases considerably for all materials, indicating increased brittleness at low temperatures. In contrast, the strength results are inconsistent, and display no clear trend across the different adhesives. These findings highlight the importance of carefully considering the response of individual materials when selecting adhesives for cryogenic applications.

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